

Synthetic Studies in the Diterpene Series. Part III.¹ Synthesis of ($\pm$)-Nimbiol Methyl Ether and its Degradation Products

D. Nasipuri and D. N. Roy

Methyl ether of ($\pm$)-nimbiol has been synthesised by two different routes. Three of its degradation products, namely, 1,1,7-trimethyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-, 1,1,7-tetramethyl-6-hydroxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-, and 1,7-dimethyl-6-hydroxy-phenanthrenes, and their derivatives have also been synthesised.

Nimbiol, a ketophenolic diterpene, was isolated from the trunk bark of *Metia azadirachta*, Linn. by Sengupta *et al.*² and its structure (I) established from a study of the various degradation products of deoxonimbiol. These consisted of two tetrahydrophenanthrene derivatives (II and III), one phenanthrol (IV), and pimarane (1,7-dimethylphenanthrene). The resistance of tetrahydrophenanthrenes of the type (II and III) towards further dehydrogenation is already well known, having its precedent in the isolation of similar compounds from totaryl methyl ether^{4,5}, dextropimaric acid^{6,7}, and related natural products⁸. In view of the unusual structure of nimbiol, which does not correspond to a fully diterpenoid formula, we were interested in synthesising these degradation products on which the structure was based, and also nimbiol methyl ether itself, following a method reported earlier⁹. The research, however, was delayed and meanwhile a few syntheses of nimbiol and its methyl ether appeared¹⁰⁻¹², including one¹³ along the general route reported by us⁹. The latter synthesis¹³, though similar in essence with the one described below, differs in some significant points from ours. This together with a new alternative synthesis of ($\pm$)-nimbiol methyl ether and the synthesis of the three phenanthrene derivatives (II, III, and IV) form the subject matter of the present communication. A preliminary account of a part of this work has already been reported⁹.

The tetrahydrophenanthrenes (II and III) were synthesised from suitably substituted γ -1-naphthylbutyric esters (VII) by the action of methylmagnesium iodide and cyclodehydration of the resultant alcohol (VIII).

1. Part II, Nasipuri and Guha, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 4248.
2. Nasipuri and Roy, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1962, **B21**, 50.
3. *Chem. & Ind.*, 1958, 801; *Tetrahedron*, 1960, **10**, 45.
4. Short and Wang, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 2070.
5. Nasipuri and Chaudhuri, *ibid.*, 1968, 2579.
6. Harris and Sanderson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 2081.
7. Nasipuri and Chaudhuri, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 4299.
8. Briggs *et al.*, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1968, 599; Galik *et al.*, *Tetrahedron*, 1969, **7**, 223.
9. Nasipuri, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1957, 425.
10. Bible, *Tetrahedron*, 1960, **11**, 22.
11. Wenkert *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 2320.
12. Ramachandran and Duttia, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 4766.
13. Deloëlle and Fetizon, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1961, 1900.

Buryric esters (VII) were most conveniently prepared from the appropriate α -tetralones (V) by treatment with methyl γ -bromoacrylate in presence of zinc, followed by disproportionation of the dihydronaphthalene derivatives (VI) with palladium black¹⁴. 6-Methyltetralone (V: R=H), obtained by cyclising γ -*m*-tolylbutyric acid, was thus converted *via* the esters (VI and VII: R=H) into the alcohol (VIII: R=H), and finally into 1,1,7-trimethyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrophenanthrene (II). 7-Methoxy-6-methyl-1-tetralone¹⁵ (V: R=OMe) under similar sequence of reactions afforded 1,1,7-trimethyl-6-methoxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrophenanthrene in good yield. The corresponding phenol (III) was obtained on demethylation. In another experiment, γ -7-methoxy-6-methyl-1-naphthylbutyric acid (as VII: R=OMe) was cyclised by stannic chloride¹⁶ to 1-oxo-6-methoxy-7-methyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrophenanthrene. The latter was then converted into 1,7-dimethyl-6-methoxyphenanthrene and the corresponding phenanthrol (IV) by conventional procedure.

In all cases, the identity of these synthetic compounds with those derived from natural source³ was proved by determination of mixed melting points which remained unaltered.

A bilateral synthesis of ($\pm$)-nimbiol methyl ether by a concerted double cyclisation⁹ of the alcohols (X and XI) was next attempted. The methyl ester of 5-oxo-8-(4'-methoxy-3'-methylphenyl)octanoic acid (IX), prepared either (a) by alkylating ethyl

14. Cook and Schoental, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 288.

15. Bun-Hoi *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1950, 15, 950.

16. Haworth and Sheldrick, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 804.

β -oxopimelate¹⁷ with 4-methoxy-3-methylphenethyl bromide or (b) by condensing γ -(4-methoxy-3-methylphenyl)butyryl chloride with ethyl α -acetylglutarate¹⁸, and hydrolysing the product in each case. 4-Methoxy-3-methylphenethyl alcohol (XVI: $n=2$) required in these experiments was readily available from 4-bromo-2-methylanisole by ethylene oxide synthesis. γ -4-Methoxy-3-methylphenylpropanol (XVI: $n=3$), required for a subsequent experiment, was obtained either from the former by a process of homologation¹ or more conveniently from *o*-cresyl methyl ether by successive chloromethylation, condensation with diethyl malonate, hydrolysis, and lithium aluminium hydride reduction of the derived propionic acid.

(IX)

(X)

(XI)

(XII)

(XIII)*

(XIV)*

(XV)

(XVI)

The methyl ester of the keto-acid (IX) on treatment with an excess of methylmagnesium iodide afforded the diol (X), whereas the analogous unsaturated alcohol (XI) was prepared from γ -4-methoxy-3-methylphenylpropyl bromide and methylheptenone by the Grignard reaction¹⁹. These were separately treated with polyphosphoric acid and the product, which was almost identical in both the cases, as proved by subsequent oxidation experiment, seemed to be a complex mixture, possibly with the podocarpatriene derivative (XII)

17. Guha *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1960, 37, 287.

18. Robinson and Schlittler, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 1288.

19. Fernholz, *Chem. Ber.*, 1951, 84, 111; Horeau and Emiliozzi, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1957, 381; Bachmann *et al.*, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1959, 42, 1790.

*One enantiomer is only shown.

as one of its major component. It showed no detectable amount of unsaturation* towards catalytic hydrogenation and its ultraviolet absorption spectra ($\lambda_{\max}$ 279 m μ ; $\log \epsilon$, 3.34) were consistent broadly with the structure (XII). After a preliminary purification over alumina, it was oxidised by chromic acid¹⁰ and the product resolved into a major monoketonic fraction and two diketones. One of the latter, m.p. 163°, was characterised as the 1,4-dianisoylbutane derivative (XV) from elemental analysis, UV absorption spectra, and previous analogy, its formation being due to oxidation of a byproduct of the preceding Grignard reaction. The second diketone, m.p. 200° (yellow), isolated in nearly 5% yield, was proved to be the *cis*-diketone (XIV) by an unambiguous synthesis (*vide infra*) and was quite in accordance with the expectation. The monoketonic fraction after prolonged keeping at 0° in contact with methanol afforded a few crystals which after several recrystallisations had m.p. 112-14° and contrary to the observation of Delobelle and Fetizon¹³ were found to be identical with methyl ether of ($\pm$)-nimbiol [mixed m.p., dinitrophenylhydrazone (m.p. 232°), and infrared spectra].

The rest of the monoketonic material (liquid)[†], however, remained unidentified. It had identical UV absorption spectra as those of nimbiol methyl ether and furnished a dinitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. 271° (elemental analysis corresponding to that of nimbiol methyl ether derivative). In absence of any unsaturation, the original cyclised product could have either of the three alternative structures (XVII, XIX, XX). Structure (XVII) seems very unlikely as it involves cyclisation at a point *ortho* to a methyl group in preference to *para* in the benzene ring, although it is consistent with the spectroscopic inference of Delobelle and Fetizon¹³ that the cyclised product contains two vicinal hydrogen atoms in ring C.

*The use of paracids for the determination of unsaturation in these systems is extremely unreliable due to susceptibility of alkoxylated benzene derivatives towards these reagents¹².

†The name, isonimbiol methyl ether is proposed for it.

On the other hand, the increased nucleophilic activity of the aromatic ring in the systems (X and XI) due to presence of a methoxyl group, coupled with methyl-hyperconjugation, might lead to the formation of the naphthalene derivative (XVIII) directly *via* the appropriate carbonium ion, which can now cyclise only to provide compounds (XIX and XX). This view seems to be in harmony with the fact that alcohols (XXI: R=H; R'=OMe)²¹ and (XXI: R=Pr⁴; R'=OMe)¹, which do not have the methyl-hyperconjugation, cyclise normally to the podocarpatriene system, whereas a preliminary experiment in our laboratory²² on the cyclisation of an analogous compound (XXI: R=OMe; R'=H) where the electron-releasing effect of the methoxyl group is in full force at the reaction site, seems to indicate the almost exclusive formation of an abnormal product. We intend to discuss this point in future when more data are available.*

Formation of the undesirable products, discussed above, could be largely avoided if the starting material contained the ring A preformed. Accordingly, 4-methoxy-3-methylbenzaldehyde was condensed with methyl isopropyl ketone and the product (XXII) treated with 1-N-diethylaminopentan-3-one²³ according to a known procedure²⁴. The unsaturated ketone (XXIII), thus obtained, was reduced catalytically and the resultant crystalline cyclohexanone derivative (XXIV) on lithium aluminium hydride reduction, followed by cyclodehydration, furnished a stereoisomeric mixture of deoxonimbiol methyl ether (XII). This was oxidised and the product separated into two clean-cut fragments: 5 α -12-methoxy-13-methyl-7-oxopodocarpa-8,11,13-triene (XIII) (60%), identical with ($\pm$)-nimbiol methyl ether and 5 β -12-methoxy-13-methyl-6,7-dioxopodocarpa-8,11,13-triene (XIV) (15%) along with a small amount of the unchanged starting material. The diketone was found to be identical with the one previously described.

The structures of the major cyclised product of the alcohols (X and XI) are now being investigated spectroscopically. The synthesis of the compounds of the type (XVIII and XIX) is also in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL

3-Methylphenethyl Alcohol.—To a cooled Grignard reagent, prepared from 3-iodotoluene (58 g.), magnesium (16 g.), and ether (400 ml), was added with stirring a solution of ethylene oxide (25 g.) in ether (50 ml) within 1 hour. The solid complex formed was gently refluxed for 2 hrs. and then decomposed in the usual way with cold H₂SO₄ (dil.). The ethereal layer was separated, washed with water, dehydrated (Na₂SO₄), and the solvent removed. The residue on distillation afforded 3-methylphenethyl alcohol (28 g.), b.p. 112°/10 mm. It formed a 3,5-dinitrobenzoate which crystallised in yellow needles, m.p. 107°. (Found: C, 57.9; H, 4.4; N, 8.7. C₁₆H₁₄O₆N₂ requires C, 58.1; H, 4.2; N, 8.5%).

The corresponding bromide was prepared by treating the alcohol with PBr₃ in the usual way and had b.p. 110°/17 mm.

The hydrophenalene structure (as XIX) for the alternative cyclisation products has now been confirmed by NMR data and also by synthesis, which will appear in a future communication—added in proofs.

21. *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1961, 1894.

22. Nasipuri and Pyne, unpublished work.

23. Adamson *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1576.

24. Church *et al.*, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1960, 17, 1; Aktar and Woodon, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 4058.

γ-m-Tolylbutyric Acid.—The above bromide (14 g.) was condensed with diethyl malonate (15 g.) in presence of ethanolic sodium ethoxide from sodium (1.6 g.) and absolute ethanol (35 ml) by heating the mixture on a water bath for 8 hours. The product (14 g.), b.p. 175-80°/14mm, on being heated with 20% ethanolic KOH (60 ml), afforded the substituted malonic acid (9.1 g.), m.p. 146°, which on decarboxylation at 170° for 1 hour gave *γ-m-tolylbutyric acid* (7.5 g.), b.p. 165°/15mm, m.p. 39-40°. (Found: C, 73.8; H, 8.2. $C_{11}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 74.1; H, 7.8%.)

6-Methyl-1-tetralone (V: R=H).—The acid chloride, b.p. 165°/12 mm (6 g.), of the preceding acid in dry CS_2 (45 ml) was allowed to react with powdered aluminium chloride (9 g.) at 0°. The product was worked up in the usual way to afford the *tetralone* (V: R=H) (5 g.), b.p. 125°/10 mm, as a viscous oil. It gave a *DNP*, m.p. 249° (from benzene-light petroleum. (Found: C, 59.8; H, 4.8; N, 16.3. $C_{17}H_{16}O_2N_4$ requires C, 60.0; H, 4.7; N, 16.5%.)

Methyl γ-3,4-Dihydro-6-methyl-1-naphthylcrotonate (VI: R=H).—A mixture of amalgamated zinc wool (4.2 g.), methyl *γ*-bromocrotonate²⁵ (9.5 g.), the above tetralone (5 g.), and dry thiophene-free benzene (25 ml) was heated under reflux on the water bath for 1 hour and then decomposed with crushed ice (50 g.) and HCl (dil., 50 ml). The benzene layer was separated, the aqueous layer once more extracted with benzene, and the combined benzene extracts were washed with dilute Na_2CO_3 , then with water, dried (Na_2SO_4), and the solvent removed. The residue on distillation provided the ester (VI: R=H) (3 g.), b.p. 190°/1.5mm. (Found: C, 78.9; H, 7.0. $C_{16}H_{18}O_2$ requires C, 79.3; H, 7.4%). The corresponding acid, obtained by hydrolysis, crystallised from aqueous methanol in white prisms, m.p. 229°. (Found: C, 78.9; H, 7.2. $C_{15}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 78.9; H, 7.0%.)

Methyl γ-6-Methyl-1-naphthylbutyrate (VII: R=H).—The ester (VI: R=H) (3 g.) and palladium black (200 mg.) were heated at 280-300° under carbon dioxide for 3 hours and the mixture extracted with hot benzene. After removal of the benzene, the residue (3 g.) was hydrolysed by 10% ethanolic KOH solution to *γ-6-Methyl-1-naphthylbutyric acid* (2.5 g.), m.p. 136° (aqueous methanol). (Found: C, 78.6; H, 7.2. $C_{15}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 78.9; H, 7.0%). The acid, thus obtained, was esterified with diazomethane and the ester (VII: R=H), b.p. 200°/1.5 mm, was used in the next operation.

1,1,7-Trimethyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrophenanthrene (II).—The foregoing ester (1.1 g.) was treated with an excess of MeMgI in ethereal solution. The crude alcohol (VIII: R=H), thus obtained, was treated with polyphosphoric acid, prepared from P_2O_5 (2 g.) and 89% H_3PO_4 (10 ml), at 170° for 3 hours. The red solution was decomposed with crushed ice, organic matter thoroughly extracted with ether, the ethereal layer washed with 4% aqueous NaOH and then with water, dried, and the solvent evaporated. The residue (0.7 g.) was taken up in petroleum (b.p. 60-80°) and passed through a column of activated alumina. Thus purified, product (II) was obtained as a white solid which on crystallisation from methanol afforded colorless plates, m.p. 82°. (Found: C, 90.9; H, 8.8. Calc. for $C_{17}H_{20}$: C, 91.1; H, 8.9%). Sengupta *et al.*³ report m.p. 82-83°. The hydrocarbon afforded a *dicarboxylate* as red needles from absolute ethanol, m.p. 90-91°. (Found: N, 9.0. $C_{15}H_{18}O_4N_2$ requires N, 9.2%.)

Methyl γ-3,4-dihydro-7-methoxy-6-methyl-1-naphthylcrotonate (VI: R=OMe) was prepared from *γ*-7-methoxy-6-methyl-1-tetralone (V: R=OMe) by the action of methyl

γ -bromocrotonate in presence of zinc by following the method described before and obtained as a crystalline solid, m.p. 117-18°. (Found: C, 75.1; H, 7.2. $C_{17}H_{20}O_3$ requires C, 75.0; H, 7.3%). The derived acid had m.p. 205-206°. (Found: C, 73.9; H, 6.8. $C_{16}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 74.4; H, 7.0%).

The corresponding *methyl γ -1-naphthylbutyrate* (VII: R=OMe) was prepared by heating the crotonic ester (VI: R=OMe) with palladium black. The *methyl ester*, b.p. 210°/10mm, crystallised from light petroleum (b.p. 40-60°) in colorless prisms, m.p. 87°. (Found: C, 74.7; H, 7.1. $C_{17}H_{20}O_3$ requires C, 75.0; H, 7.3%). The *acid* (as VII: R=OMe), obtained on hydrolysis, crystallised from aqueous methanol in white nodules, m.p. 145°. (Found: C, 74.0; H, 6.7. $C_{16}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 74.4; H, 7.0%).

1,1,7-Trimethyl-6-hydroxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrophenanthrene (III).—The methyl ester (VII: R=OMe) (1.6 g.) was treated with an excess of $MeMgI$ in ether and the crude alcohol (VIII: R=OMe) was cyclised by polyphosphoric acid, prepared as already mentioned, at 170° for 3 hours. *1,1,7-Trimethyl-6-methoxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrophenanthrene*, thus obtained, was purified by elution through activated alumina and finally crystallised from ethanol in fine needles, m.p. and mixed m.p. 148°. (Found: C, 84.9; H, 8.4. Calc. for $C_{18}H_{22}O$: C, 85.0; H, 8.6%). The free *phenol* (III), obtained on demethylation with boiling aniline hydrochloride, crystallised from benzene-petroleum (b.p. 60-80°) in fine white needles, m.p. and mixed m.p. with that derived from natural source, 149°. Sengupta *et al.*³ report m.p. 148°. The mixed m.p. of the phenol and its methyl ether was 128-30°.

1-Oxo-6-methoxy-7-methyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrophenanthrene.— γ -7-Methoxy-6-methyl-1-naphthylbutyric acid (3 g.) was heated with anhydrous stannic chloride (8 ml) at 100° for 1 hour. The cooled mixture was decomposed with HCl (dil.), the organic matter extracted with ether, washed with 2% aqueous NaOH and then with water, and dried (Na_2SO_4). After evaporation of the solvent, the keto-phenanthrene was obtained as a brown solid and finally crystallised from benzene-petroleum (b.p. 60-80°) in white flakes (1.8 g.), m.p. 169°. (Found: C, 80.0; H, 6.9. $C_{16}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 80.0; H, 6.7%). The *semicarbazone* readily formed from dilute ethanol and crystallised from the same solvent as white nodules, m.p. 290°. (Found: N, 14.0. $C_{17}H_{19}O_2N_3$ requires N, 14.1%).

1,7-Dimethyl-6-hydroxyphenanthrene (IV).—The foregoing ketone (1.6 g.) was treated with $MeMgI$, prepared from magnesium (2.2 g.), methyl iodide (3.2 ml), and dry ether (50 ml). Dry benzene (50 ml) was then added and the whole refluxed on the water bath for 4 hours. The cooled mixture was decomposed with H_2SO_4 (dil.) and the product worked up as usual to furnish the crude *alcohol* (1.4 g.) as a solid, m.p. 108-10°. This was intimately mixed with 10% palladium charcoal (1 g.) and heated at 300-320° in a metal bath for 2 hours. The melt was extracted repeatedly with hot benzene, the benzene solution filtered, solvent evaporated, and the residue eluted through alumina by petroleum (b.p. 60-80°). After evaporation of the solvent, the material was crystallised from benzene-petroleum (b.p. 60-80°) to provide the compound (IV) in thin plates (450 mg.), m.p. 123-24°. (Found: C, 86.1; H, 6.4. Calc. for $C_{17}H_{16}O$: C, 86.4; H, 6.8%). It formed a *trinitrobenzene* derivative which crystallised from ethanol in orange-red needles, m.p. 177°. (Found: C, 61.4; H, 4.3. $C_{23}H_{19}O_7N_3$ requires C, 61.5; H, 4.2%).

After separation of the methyl ether, the column was next eluted with benzene and a white solid (150 mg., m.p. 190°) was obtained. This crystallised from benzene-petroleum

(60-80°) in tiny plates, m.p. 191°; it was identical with compound (IV). (Found: C, 86.2; H, 6.4. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{14}O$: C, 86.5; H, 6.3%). The demethylation occurred evidently by the action of $MeMgI$ during the preceding Grignard reaction. The phenol was heated with dimethyl sulphate, anhydrous potassium carbonate, and acetone to furnish a methyl ether, m.p. 123-24°, identical with that described previously. Songupta *et al.*³ report 189-190° and 119-20° as the m.p.s. of the phenol (IV) and its methyl ether respectively.

3-Methyl-4-methoxyphenethyl Alcohol (XVI: $n=2$).—4-Bromo-2-methylanisole was prepared by brominating *o*-cresyl methyl ether (50 g.) in acetic acid (500 ml) with a solution of bromine (22 ml) in acetic acid (150 ml) at room temperature. The crystalline solid separating after addition of crushed ice was filtered, washed with water, dried, and crystallised from benzene in white plates (75 g.), m.p. 68°. The Grignard reagent, prepared from 4-bromo-2-methylanisole (60 g.), magnesium (8.5 g.), and dry ether (200 ml), was treated with a solution of ethylene oxide (20 g.) in ether (50 ml) in the cold. After 12 hours at room temperature, dry benzene (100 ml) was added and the whole refluxed gently for 2 hours, it was then cooled, decomposed with H_2SO_4 (dil.), and the product worked up in the usual way. The alcohol (XVI: $n=2$) was obtained as a colorless oil (27 g.), b.p. 120°/8 mm. (Found: C, 72.1; H, 8.2. $C_{16}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 72.3; H, 8.4%). The 3,5-dinitrobenzoate crystallised from ethanol in yellow prismatic needles, m.p. 162°. (Found: C, 56.2; H, 4.1; N, 7.4. $C_{17}H_{16}O_7N_2$ requires C, 56.6; H, 4.4; N, 7.8%).

The corresponding bromide (20 g.), b.p. 110°/8 mm, was obtained⁶ as a highly refracting liquid by the action of PBr_3 (21.5 g.) on the alcohol (27 g.) in dry CCl_4 (50 ml) at 60° for 15 minutes.

5-Ox-8-(3-methyl-4-methoxyphenyl)octanoic Acid (IX).—(a). Ethyl β -oxopimelate (11 g.) and the preceding bromide (10.4 g.) were heated with sodium (1.1 g.) in ethanol (70 ml) at 90° for 15 hours to provide ethyl α -(3-methyl-4-methoxyphenethyl)- β -oxopimelate (8 g.), b.p. 210-20°/1.5 mm. It was hydrolysed by heating with a solution of NaOH (4 g.) in water (160 ml) for 6 hours. The mixture was cooled, any neutral material removed by extraction with ether, and the alkaline solution acidified. The gummy acid (IX), thus obtained, was directly esterified with refluxing 3% methanolic HCl (80 ml) to furnish the methyl ester (as IX) (5.3 g.), b.p. 195°/1.5 mm. (Found: C, 69.5; H, 8.0. $C_{17}H_{24}O_4$ requires C, 69.8; H, 8.2%). The acid (IX), obtained on hydrolysis, crystallised from aqueous methanol in needles, m.p. 68-70°. (Found: C, 68.9; H, 7.9; equiv., 280. $C_{16}H_{22}O_4$ requires C, 69.0; H, 8.0%; equiv., 278). It gave a semicarbazone, m.p. 163°. (Found: N, 12.3. $C_{17}H_{25}O_4N_3$ requires N, 12.5%).

(b). γ -3-Methyl-4-methoxyphenylbutyryl chloride (17 g.) in dry ether (40 ml) was added in the cold to a suspension of sodio-derivative of ethyl α -acetylglutarate, prepared from the β -oxo-ester (17.5 g.), pulverised sodium (1.8 g.), and ether (150 ml); the mixture was left overnight. Next day, it was gently refluxed on the water bath for 1 hour, cooled, decomposed with H_2SO_4 (dil.), the ether layer separated, and washed with water. After evaporation of the solvent, the residue was hydrolysed⁶ by 3% aqueous KOH for 16 hours to furnish the acid (IX) (10 g.), m.p. 68-70°, identical with that prepared by method (a).

γ-3-Methyl-4-methoxyphenylpropan-1-ol (XVI; $n=3$).—(a). 3-Methyl-4-methoxyphenethyl bromide (27 g.) was heated with an ethanolic solution of sodium cyanide (25 g.) to afford 3-methyl-4-methoxyphenethyl cyanide (20 g.), b.p. 145°/8 mm. The cyanide (20 g.) was next converted by the action of boiling methanolic HCl into methyl β-3-methyl-4-methoxyphenylpropionate (20 g.), b.p. 140°/8 mm, which crystallised from benzene-light petroleum (b.p. 40-60°) in thick prisms, m.p. 47°. (Found: C, 69.0; H, 7.9. $C_{12}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 69.2; H, 7.7%). The derived acid had m.p. 100°. (Found: C, 68.1; H, 7.4. $C_{11}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 68.0; H, 7.2%). The methyl ester (15 g.), m.p. 47°, was reduced by $LiAlH_4$ (4g.) in dry ether (200 ml) to furnish the alcohol (XVI; $n=3$) (11 g.), b.p. 136/6 mm. It solidified on keeping and crystallised from light petroleum in white needles, m.p. 45°. (Found: C, 73.0; H, 9.0. $C_{11}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 73.3; H, 8.9%). It formed a 3,5-dinitrobenzoate which crystallised from aqueous methanol in yellow needles, m.p. 102°. (Found: C, 58.0; H, 5.0. $C_{16}H_{19}O_7N_2$ requires C, 57.7; H, 4.8%).

(b). 3-Methyl-4-methoxybenzyl chloride (30 g.), b.p. 102°/10 mm, obtained by chloromethylation²⁷ of *o*-cresyl methyl ether, was condensed with diethyl malonate (30 g.) by heating with a solution of sodium (3.8 g.) in ethanol (70 ml) for 10 hours. Diethyl 3-methyl-4-methoxybenzylmalonate (28 g.), b.p. 170°/0.5 mm, thus obtained, was hydrolysed by KOH (22 g.) in 95% ethanol (110 ml.) on the water bath for 4 hours. Ethanol was removed in the water pump. Acidification of the alkaline solution afforded the substituted malonic acid (23 g.) as a crystalline solid, m.p. 148°. (Found: C, 60.2; H, 6.0. $C_{12}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 60.5; H, 5.9%). This was heated in an oil bath at 170° for 1 hour and then distilled to furnish β-3-methyl-4-methoxyphenylpropionic acid (15 g.), b.p. 180-85°/10 mm, m.p. 100°. The acid (14 g.) was reduced by $LiAlH_4$ in the usual way to afford the alcohol (XVI; $n=3$) (10 g.), m.p. 45°, characterised by the formation of the 3,5-dinitrobenzoate, m.p. 102°.

The corresponding bromide was prepared by PBr_3 in the usual way and had b.p. 130-32°/6 mm. Delobelle and Fetizon³ record b.p. 126°/0.5 mm.

9-(3-Methyl-4-methoxyphenyl)-2,6-dimethylnonane-2,6-diol (X).—The methyl ester of (IX) (5.3 g.) in dry benzene (20 ml) was added to a Grignard reagent, prepared from magnesium (2.7 g.), MeI (8 ml), and ether (60 ml). The mixture was refluxed for 1 hour, decomposed with cold dilute acid, and the product worked up in the usual way. The crude diol (X) (5.5 g.), obtained after removal of the low-boiling fraction up to 140°/0.2 mm, was used for the subsequent cyclodehydration experiment.

1-(3-Methyl-4-methoxyphenyl)-4,8-dimethyl-non-7-en-4-ol (XI).—*γ*-3-Methyl-4-methoxyphenylpropyl bromide (8.4 g.), methylheptenone (6 g.), and magnesium (2 g.) were condensed under the usual condition to furnish the unsaturated alcohol (XI) (9 g.) after removal of the lower-boiling fraction.

Cyclodehydration of the Diol (X) and the Unsaturated Alcohol (XI).—Both the compounds were cyclised under identical conditions. The alcohol (5 g.) was mixed with polyphosphoric acid, prepared from P_2O_5 (62 g.) and 89% H_3PO_4 (40 ml), and heated at 80° with stirring for 1 hour. The product was worked up in the usual way and distilled to provide a clear viscous oil (3.5 g.), b.p. 155°/0.01 mm. A good middle fraction was analysed. (Found: C, 83.6, 83.9; H, 10.2, 10.5. Calc. for $C_{19}H_{28}O$: C, 83.8; H, 10.3%). λ_{max}^{EtOH} 279 μ .

27. Quelet and Anglade, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1836, 2200.

(log ϵ , 3.34); $\lambda_{\min}$ 251 μ (log ϵ , 3.03). An attempt to isolate any crystalline material by chromatography over activated alumina failed.

($\pm$)-*Nimbiol Methyl Ether* (XIII).—The foregoing cyclised product (2 g.) in glacial acetic acid (25 ml) was added to a solution of chromic acid (2.5 g.) in 80% aqueous acetic acid (32 ml). After 24 hours at room temperature, the dark green solution was diluted, the organic matter taken up in ether; the ethereal layer was washed with water and dried. The residue after evaporation of the solvent was chromatographed in light petroleum on activated alumina. The petroleum fraction consisted of a non-ketonic material (0.4-0.5 g.) and was discarded. A benzene eluate was next collected and on evaporation afforded a mono-ketonic material (1.1 g.). This gave a *dinitrophenylhydrazones*, m.p. 195-210° which after repeated crystallisations from ethyl acetate-methanol furnished dark red needles, m.p. 271° (decomp.). (Found: C, 64.3; H, 6.5; N, 12.2. $C_{25}H_{30}O_3N_4$ requires C, 64.3; H, 6.4; N, 12.0%). $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{chlf}}$ 397 μ (log ϵ , 4.45).

The above ketonic material (1.1 g.) could not be further separated by chromatography, but after prolonged keeping in the refrigerator in contact with a few drops of methanol afforded needle-shaped crystals (25 mg.), m.p. 100-107°. These were collected and after a few more crystallisations from aqueous methanol had m.p. 114-16°. (Found: C, 79.5; H, 9.0. Calc. for $C_{19}H_{26}O_2$: C, 79.7; H, 9.1%). $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 275 μ (log ϵ , 4.07); $\lambda_{\min}$ 245 μ (log ϵ , 3.26). It gave a DNP which crystallised from ethyl acetate-methanol in needles, m.p. 232°. (Found C, 64.5; H, 6.5; N, 11.9. Calc. for $C_{25}H_{30}O_3N_4$: C, 64.3; H, 6.4; N, 12.0%). $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{chlf}}$ 399 μ (log ϵ , 4.4). The I.R. spectra of the above ketone were identical with those of ($\pm$)-nimbiol methyl ether, synthesised by a different route (*vide infra*). There was no depression of m.p.s. of the ketone and its DNP, when mixed with authentic samples, kindly provided by Dr. Dutta¹².

The mother liquor after separation of ($\pm$)-nimbiol methyl ether formed a DNP, m.p. 271° (*vide supra*). An attempt to regenerate the ketone from this derivative by the action of pyruvic acid in presence of hydrogen bromide¹³ apparently failed.

1,4-Di-(3-methyl-4-methoxybenzoyl)butane (XV).—A second benzene fraction of the preceding chromatogram afforded a diketone (50 mg.) which crystallised from benzene-light petroleum in almost colorless needles, m.p. 163°; $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 275 μ (log ϵ , 4.38); $\lambda_{\min}$ 240 μ (log ϵ , 3.6). It is in most probability identical with the compound (XV). (Found: C, 74.3; H, 7.6. $C_{22}H_{26}O_4$ requires C, 74.6; H, 7.3%).

5 β -($\pm$)-13-Methyl-12-methoxy-6,7-dioxopodocarpa-8,11,13-triene (XIV).—The yellow material, still adhered to the chromatogram, was finally moved down by elution with ethanol. After evaporation of the solvent, a yellow crystalline solid (*ca.* 20 mg.), m.p. 197-98°, was obtained which crystallised from methanol to afford the 5 β -diketone, (XIV) in fine yellow needles, m.p. 200°. (Found: C, 75.9; H, 4.1. $C_{19}H_{24}O_6$ requires C, 76.0; H, 8.07%). $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 225, 249, and 349 μ (log ϵ , 3.87, 3.70, and 4.0 respectively); $\lambda_{\min}$ in 2 α and 269 μ (log ϵ , 3.66 and 2.93 respectively).

3-Methyl-4-methoxybenzaldehyde was obtained by the Gattermann synthesis¹⁴ from *o*-cresyl methyl ether in about 65% yield as a colorless oil, b.p. 110°/12 mm. and

28. Banerjee *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1957, 34, 715.

29. Gattermann and Frenzel, *Ber.*, 1898, 31, 1150.

characterised by the formation of a DNP, m.p. 231°. (Found: C, 54.6; H, 4.0; N, 16.7. $C_{15}H_{14}O_5N_4$ requires C, 54.5; H, 4.2; N, 16.9%.)

1-(3-Methyl-4-methoxyphenyl)-4-methylpent-1-en-3-one (XXII).—A mixture of 3-methyl-4-methoxybenzaldehyde (15 g.), methyl isopropyl ketone³⁰ (8 g.), 95% ethanol (40 ml), water (13 ml), and 10% aqueous NaOH (10 ml) was shaken at room temperature for 24 hours. The product was diluted with water, the heavy organic layer taken in ether, washed with water, and dried. The residue after evaporation of the solvent was distilled to provide the styryl ketone (XXII) (17 g., 70%), b.p. 180-85°/0.4mm. (Found: C, 77.2; H, 8.1. $C_{14}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 77.0; H, 8.3%). The DNP crystallised from benzene-methanol in red prisms, m.p. 203°. (Found: N, 13.9. $C_{20}H_{24}O_5N_4$ requires N, 14.1%).

2,4,4-Trimethyl-3-(3-methyl-4-methoxystyryl)cyclohex-2-en-1-one (XXIII).—A solution of the preceding ketone (XXII) (8 g.) in dry benzene (15 ml) was added to the methiodide of 1-N-diethylaminopentan-3-one, prepared from the aminoketone (7 g.) and methyl iodide (3 ml). The mixture was cooled and into it was introduced gradually a solution of potassium ethoxide (from potassium, 3 g.) in absolute ethanol (50 ml) with vigorous shaking. After 4 hours in the room temperature, the reaction mixture was gently refluxed on a water bath for 4 hours more, cooled, decomposed with 2N- H_2SO_4 (100 ml), and the organic matter extracted with benzene. The benzene layer was washed with dilute acid, then with water, dried (Na_2SO_4), and the solvent evaporated. The residue on distillation afforded the cyclohexanone derivative (XXIII) (5 g.), b.p. 180-95°/0.6mm, as a viscous liquid. The DNP crystallised from benzene-methanol as a deep red powder, m.p. 200°. (Found: C, 64.5; H, 6.3; N, 12.5. $C_{23}H_{28}O_5N_4$ requires C, 64.6; H, 6.0; N, 12.1%).

2,4,4-Trimethyl-3-(3-methyl-4-methoxyphenethyl)cyclohexan-1-one (XXIV).—The foregoing unsaturated ketone (4 g.) was reduced catalytically by shaking in an atmosphere of hydrogen in presence of 10% palladium-charcoal at room temperature. The first mole of hydrogen was absorbed rapidly (2 hours), followed by a slower absorption (6 hours) of a second mole of hydrogen. The solution was filtered and distilled to afford the cyclohexanone derivative (XXIV) (4 g.), b.p. 180°/0.4 mm, which crystallised from petroleum (b.p. 60-80°) in plates (2.4 g.). m.p. 81°. (Found: C, 79.4; H, 9.5. $C_{19}H_{26}O_4$ requires C, 79.1; H, 9.7%). λ_{max}^{EtOH} 225 and 278 μ ($\log \epsilon$, 3.96 and 3.29 respectively). The DNP, formed readily, crystallised from benzene-methanol in orange needles, m.p. 139°. (Found: C, 64.2; H, 6.8; N, 11.8. $C_{25}H_{32}O_5N_4$ requires C, 64.1; H, 6.8; N, 11.9%).

(±)-13-Methyl-12-methoxy podocarpa-8,11,13-triene (XII).—The foregoing ketone (1 g.) was reduced by $LiAlH_4$ (0.5 g.) in dry ether (25 ml) and the resultant alcohol was cyclodehydrated by polyphosphoric acid, prepared from P_2O_5 (12.5 g.) and 89% H_3PO_4 (8 ml), at 80° for 1 hour. The product was worked up in the usual way, chromatographed over activated alumina (50 g.) using light petroleum as solvent, and finally distilled to afford the triene (XII) (0.7 g.), b.p. 150°/0.2 mm. (Found: C, 83.6; H, 10.1. Calc. for $C_{19}H_{26}O$: C, 83.8; H, 10.3%). λ_{max}^{EtOH} 279 μ ($\log \epsilon$, 3.31).

(±)-Nimbiol Methyl Ether (XIII) and the Diketone (XIV).—The above compound (XII) (700 mg.) was oxidised by chromic acid in acetic acid, as described before, and the product chromatographed over activated alumina (80 g.). The light petroleum fraction afforded a neutral gummy matter (30 mg.) which was rejected. The ketone

fraction (500 mg.), eluted by benzene, solidified and on crystallisation from methanol afforded the ether (XIII) in needles, m.p. 114-16°. (Found: C, 78.7; H, 8.8%). $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 230 and 276 m μ (log ϵ , 4.10 and 4.10). The *DNP* crystallised from ethyl acetate-methanol in fine red needles, m.p. 232°. (Found: C, 64.3; H, 6.5; N, 12.0). The *semicarbazone* crystallised from ethanol in glistening plates, m.p. 188-90°. (Found: C, 69.9; H, 8.5. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{29}\text{O}_2\text{N}_3$ requires C, 69.9; H, 8.4%). It turned yellow on keeping. The mixed m.p.s of the above ketone and the dinitrophenylhydrazone with the authentic specimens¹² (m.p.s 117-18° and 232° respectively) remained undepressed.

The yellow zone on the chromatogram was eluted by ethanol. Evaporation of the solvent afforded the yellow *diketone* (XIV) (130 mg.) which crystallised from methanol in thin needles, m.p. 200°. (Found: C, 75.9; H, 8.0%).

The authors are indebted to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi, for a fellowship (to D. N.R.), to Drs. P. Sengupta and H. N. Khastgir for a gift of samples derived from the natural source, to Prof. P. C. Dutta of the Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science for a gift of ($\pm$)-nimbiol methyl ether and its dinitrophenylhydrazone, and to Sri B. Bhattacharya and Sri R. N. Chakravarti of the University College of Science for microanalyses.

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY,
CALCUTTA-9.

Received November 29, 1962.